

Prevalence of acid-resistant Verotoxin-producing *Escherichia coli* associated with diarrhea

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Summary

Diarrhea is a significant health issue in many countries, where it is considered one of the prominent causes of morbidity. *Escherichia coli* is one of the many enteropathogenic bacteria which causes seasonal diarrhea. This study aimed to look at the prevalence of Verotoxin-producing *E. coli* (VTEC) in fecal samples taken from patients with acute diarrhea and their antibiotic resistance profile. A total of 75 strains of *E. coli* were isolated from fecal samples collected from patients with acute diarrhea using phenotypic methods. The antibiotic susceptibility pattern

of all isolates was determined by the disk agar diffusion method. 57 (90%) VTEC isolates were confirmed; all VTEC isolates were acid-resistant (pH3). High antibiotic resistance was observed for cefoxitin (100%), polymyxin B (90%), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (86%), and tetracycline (73%). Low resistance levels were observed for chloramphenicol C (18%) and gentamicin CN (10%). Our results show that strains of *E. coli*, a major cause of diarrhea, need to be routinely checked for prevalence of antibiotic resistance.

Key words

bloody Diarrhea, EHEC, *Escherichia coli*,
Verotoxin, antimicrobial resistance

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Introduction

Enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (EPEC) is a gram-negative bacterium that can cause human disease and remains a significant cause of mortality in developing countries, including Libya.^{1,2} However, EPEC has been classified according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) into six major categories include enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC), Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC), enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC), and enteroaggregative *E. coli* (EAEC).³ Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC) or Vero-toxin Producing *E. coli* (VTEC) is a zoonotic and foodborne pathogen that can directly or indirectly be transmitted and cause diarrhea in lower-income countries, especially among children. Moreover, it has been reported that VTEC is one of the most common serogroups associated with many outbreaks and sporadic diarrheal cases worldwide.^{4,5}

VTEC serotypes can resist acidic gastric conditions, and therefore this serotype can breach the acidic barrier to stay at the ileum and colon and induce disease.^{6,7} Furthermore, VTEC serotypes may enhance the production of Verotoxin due to prior exposure to sub-

lethal pH conditions along with the consumption of amino acid as glutamate.⁸

Recently, multidrug-resistant (MDR) *E. coli* serotypes have frequently been isolated and are considered one of the major issues in healthcare settings worldwide.⁹⁻¹¹ MDR is one of the most significant global health concerns, particularly in developing countries where antibiotics quality, distribution, and usage in healthcare settings are not well controlled. Recently, the resistance pattern of *E. coli* serotypes has garnered the attention of many researchers who have documented different resistance patterns.^{12,13} Certain authors¹⁴ reported strains of toxin-producing *E. coli* that were resistant to more than nine classes of antibiotics. The resistance of toxin-producing *E. coli* isolated from contaminated food to Polymyxin B has also been documented.^{15,16}

Studying the prevalence of VTEC serotypes and their antibiotic profile may require immunological and molecular techniques, which are not available in developing countries;¹⁷ this may explain the shortage of reports about the incidence and prevalence of many pathogenic bacteria in general and VTEC in particular among patients suffering from diarrhea. Therefore, this study aims to use phenotypic methods to

study the prevalence of acid-resistant VTEC strains isolated from patients suffering from diarrhea attending the reference laboratory in Sebha city, Libya. In addition, we aimed in this study to ascertain to what extent VTEC clinical isolates are resistant to antibiotics.

Materials and methods

1. Study design and sample collection

The study was conducted with random non-replicate stool samples from February 2021 to June 2021 at the department of microbiology in the central reference laboratory of Sebha (CRLS), which is considered the prime reference laboratory in the south of Libya region and receives a mean of 19-25 stool samples per month from all public and private health care facilities. Ninety stool samples were collected from out-patients (OP) attending CRLS with an approved request from the attending physician to perform stool culture; only patients suffering from symptoms of abdominal pain, fever, and continuous diarrhea was selected to the study. A CLRS certified medical technician was responsible for sample collection instruction: the patient was given a sterile spoon bottle and advised to put clean toilet paper for stool collection without urine. Ninety OP of both genders were included in this study. The specimens collected for this study were divided into three groups according to patient age (group 1 $\geq 10 - \leq 15$ years; group 2 $\geq 29 - 40$ years; group 3 $\geq 41 - 65$ years). Epidemiological and clinical parameters that were evaluated included the firm or soft consistency of stool samples, current and previous gastro-intestinal disease history, demographic location, travel history, dietary habits, the recent use of antibiotics and gastric acid-altering medications, as well as the presence of other bacterial species such as non-lactose fermenter and gram-positive bacteria. After samples' receipt, they were immediately transported to the Microbiology Laboratory of the Faculty of Science at Sebha University for microbiological analysis.

2. Microbiological analysis

A total of 90 stool samples were collected from different people complaining of diarrhea. The consistency of stool samples was examined for blood or mucus. The samples were then inoculated into Violet red bile lactose agar (VRLBA) deep agar tubes for 24hrs at 37°C for enumeration of *E. coli*. For selective isolation of Enteropathogenic *E. coli*, the samples were then subcultured on Sorbitol MacConkey agar supplemented with cefixime and tellurite to differentiate between Enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC) and non-invasive *E.*

coli based on sorbitol fermentation.¹⁸ Gram stain of the collection was applied for identification of the organisms. Biochemical tests (e.g., indole production and citrate utilization) were also studied for the whole collection. For further confirmation, API20E strip test (Biomérieux, Italy) and coliform chrome agar (Liofilchem) were used in this study.

3. Phenotypic detection of Verotoxin producing *E. coli*

For the phenotypic detection and confirmation of Verotoxin *E. coli*, We adapted the VTEC agar described by Gill.¹⁹ The previously confirmed *E. coli* isolates were sub-cultured in VTEC agar and were incubated at 37°C \pm for 24Hrs. The growth of colourless colonies with fluorescence under UV (Vilber lourmat UV lamp, France) indicated a positive result for VTEC.

4. Glutamate dependent acid resistance assay (GSA)

The test was done according to Bhagwat²⁰ with slight modification to determine the acid resistance of *E. coli*. Minimal medium (MM) was prepared with the following formula: sodium phosphate Na₂HPO₄ 33g, potassium dihydrogen phosphate KH₂PO₄ 15g, sodium chloride NaCl 2.5g, yeast extract 4g, ammonium sulfate (NH₄)₂SO₄ 5g per liter. After sterilization, media was cooled down and supplemented with filtered glutamate (1.5mM). The pH of the MM medium was adjusted with 5N HCl to pH 3. Suspensions of the isolates were adjusted to Mac 0.5 standard and incubated for two hours at 37°C. The growth of the organisms on MM medium pH 3 indicated a glutamate-dependent acid resistance. The percentage of survival represented three trials in overnight cultures.

5. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed by Kirby-Bauer protocol (disk diffusion) method according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute²¹ recommendations by using Muller Hinton Agar (MHA). The following antimicrobial disks (Bioanalyse Co. ITALY) were used: Amoxicillin/Clavulanic Acid AUG (85µg), Cefoxitin FOX (30µg), Imipenem IMP (10µg), Tetracycline TE (10µg), Chloramphenicol C (30µg), Ciprofloxacin CIP (5µg) Gentamicin CN (25ug) Polymyxin B PB (30000UI). McFarland 0.5 turbidity standard was used in this test. Plates were incubated at 37°C \pm 2 for 16 to 18 hours. The diameter of the inhibition zone was measured in millimeters, and the result was interpreted based on CRLS performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.²¹

6. Statical analysis

Minitab version 19 (Minitab LLC) software was used

for statistical analysis. Percentages in the ages of patients among the study were analyzed, as well as differences in gender ratio specimens testing positive for total EHEC percentage within every age group (group 1 $\geq 10 - \leq 15$ years; group 2 $\geq 29 - 40$ years; group 3 $\geq 41 - 65$ years). t-test was employed to compare antimicrobial resistance results and the prevalence of mean bacterial isolates (EHEC and VTEC) in total study stool samples; a P-value was considered indicative of significance if it was equal to or less than 0.05.

7. Ethics approval

The study was approved in accordance to the Medical Committee of CRLS (00-01-2019) and by Scientific Affairs Office, Microbiology Department, Faculty of Science, Sebha university (018-19).

Result

1. Prevalence of EHEC among study stool samples

Out of 90 stool samples examined, 54 (73%) EHEC isolates were recorded among group 1 ($\geq 10 - \leq 15$ years), the majority of this group was female: 44 (82%), and the remaining were male 10 (18%). Respectively, 14 (18%) EHEC isolates were in group 2 ($\geq 29 - 40$ years), 10 (57%) were females, and 8 males (43%). The last group ($\geq 41 - 65$ years) showed the lowest EHEC isolates percentage 7 (9%), 6 (88%) were males, and 1 (12%) was female. The difference between samples was significant and P-Value was ≤ 0.05 .

2. Phenotypic detection of VTEC

Our results showed that a total of 75 isolates were confirmed as EHEC according to fermentation of sorbitol, we characterized 57/75 (90%) strains as VTEC using the phenotypic characteristics of VTEC agar, and only 18/75 (5%) strains of EHEC were not able to grow and were considered as Non-Producing Verotoxin *E. coli*, P-value < 0.05 (Fig. 1). The majority of the VTEC strains (90%) were acid-resistant by growing on MM media pH 3, and only 5% of Non-Producing Verotoxin *E. coli* was not acid-resistant (Fig. 2).

3. Antimicrobial resistance:

All strains were studied for their antibiotic resistance. Our data showed that the highest rates of resistance were for Cefoxitin (100%), Polymyxin B (90%), Amoxicillin-clavulanic Acid (86%), and Tetracycline (73%). Low resistance levels were found for Chloramphenicol (18%) and Gentamicin (10%). All strains (57) were sensitive to Imipenem and Ciprofloxacin (Fig. 3). The results were insignificant between all tested antibiotics, P-value=0.43

Discussion

Verotoxin-producing *E. coli* (VTEC) has become a severe gastrointestinal pathogen, particularly in children and the elderly.^{22 23} The most frequently isolated VTEC serotype is *E. coli* O157:H7, and this serotype is mainly found in patients with bloody diarrhea.²⁴ Moreover, it

Figure 1 Total number of VTEC producing *E. coli* isolates.

Figure 2 Frequency of VTEC producing *E. coli* isolates.

Figure 3 Percentage of antibiotic susceptibility profile among VTEC *E. coli* (IMP: Imipenem, TE: Tetracycline, FOX: Cefoxitin, PB: Polymyxin, AUG: Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, C: Chloramphenicol, CN: Gentamicin, CIP: Ciprofloxacin).

can also be associated with severe illness, leading to acute renal failure and is a major cause of hemolytic-uremic syndrome.²⁵ Transmission of VTEC can be through ingestion of undercooked food or directly from person to person by fecal-oral transmission.²⁶ However, cattle are considered the main reservoir of VTEC, and transmission to humans occurs through contaminated food and water. All strains were collected from patients suffering from bloody diarrhea

in this study, and 90% of the isolates were confirmed as VTEC strains. The leading affected group in our study was children below ten years. Our findings are similar to other reported studies.^{27,28} Our data showed that females are more prone to be infected with EHEC than males, and this finding is consistent with similar reports by other researchers.²⁹ The acid resistant nature of Verotoxin producing *E. coli* is an essential factor for this organism to survive under gastric conditions.³⁰

Moreover, the acid resistant nature of VTEC strains is related to its low infectious dose, which is estimated to be less than 100 organisms and can be attributed to the ability of the organism to survive in the gastric acid environment.³¹ Most VTEC isolates were acid-resistant, 90% in this study and only 5% were not acid-resistant. All patients with VTEC and acid resistance presented with hemorrhagic diarrhea in this study. The relationship between VTEC and bloody diarrhea has been well documented by other authors.^{22,32}

The current study highlighted the effect of many applied antibiotics on EHEC strains. Our findings reveal that all 57 VTEC strains were 100 % resistant to Cefoxitin. This result is alarming since this antibiotic is routinely prescribed to patients, particularly children.^{33,34} This result was in disagreement with reports documented by other researchers,³⁵ that demonstrated lower resistance of VTEC strains to Cefoxitin. Our study observed that the majority of VTEC strains were also resistant to Amoxicillin-clavulanic Acid, AUG (86%). Such high resistance to Amoxicillin-clavulanic Acid is not strange in countries where antibiotic misuse is common and poorly controlled. Although quinolones are not recommended for the treatment of VTEC,³⁶ we studied the response of all strains to Ciprofloxacin, and we showed that all isolates were susceptible to Ciprofloxacin. The reason behind the avoidance of β -lactam, and quinolones to treat VTEC is that the exposure of VTEC to inhibitory or sub-inhibitory concentrations of these antibiotics may enhance the host DNA damage response pathway (SOS response).³⁷ In addition, the release of verotoxin by *E. coli* is induced upon exposure to the quinolones, as authors³⁸ have documented. A high resistance rate to Tetracycline was also observed in this study. This finding was also observed by other researchers and is well documented.^{35,39}

Although Chloramphenicol is considered as contra-indicated for VTEC treatment, it can still be misused. In this study, we observed a considerable prevalence of resistance of VTEC strains against Chloramphenicol (18%). The excessive and irregular use of this antibiotic might be the reason behind such resistance pattern. Other authors have also reported the resistance of VTEC to Chloramphenicol.³⁹ Moreover, we showed in this study that the resistance of VTEC to Gentamicin is high (66.9%), a finding also reproduced by other researchers.⁴⁰

Our data showed that Imipenem was most effective against all isolates, resistance having not been developed to this antibiotic yet. The uncommon use of Imipenem in Sebha medical facilities may explain the high sensitivity of VTEC to this antibiotic. Other researchers have also documented a very high response of VTEC strains to this agent.⁴¹ So far, Imipenem is a promising antibiotic and might be considered to treat VTEC infections when necessary.

In this study, the resistance rate of VTEC strains to polymyxin B was high (90%), similar to reports from other authors.^{42 43}

Conflict of interest

None of the authors reports any conflict of interest

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Περίληψη

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Η διάρροια είναι ένα σημαντικό πρόβλημα δημόσιας υγείας σε πολλές χώρες, όπου θεωρείται μία από τις κύριες αιτίες νοσηρότητας. Το βακτήριο *Escherichia coli* είναι ένα από τα πολλά εντεροπαθογόνα βακτήρια που προκαλούν εποχική διάρροια. Η παρούσα μελέτη είχε ως στόχο να εξετάσει τον επιπολασμό του βακτηρίου *E. coli* που παράγει βεροτοξίνη (VTEC) σε δείγματα κοπράνων που ελήφθησαν από ασθενείς με οξεία διάρροια και το προφίλ αντοχής τους στα αντιμικροβιακά. Συνολικά μελετήθηκαν 75 στελέχη *E. coli* που απομονώθηκαν από δείγματα κοπράνων από ασθενείς με οξεία διάρροια. Η ταυτοποίησή τους έγινε με φαινοτυπικές μεθόδους. Το πρότυπο ευαισθησίας στα αντιμικροβιακά όλων των απομονώσεων προσδιορίστηκε με τη μέθοδο διάχυσης δίσκων αντιβιοτικών σε άγαρ. Επιβεβαιώθηκαν 57 (90%) απομονώσεις VTEC. Όλες οι απομονώσεις VTEC ήταν ανθεκτικές στα οξέα (pH3). Στα αντιμικροβιακά παρατηρήθηκε υψηλή αντοχή στην κεφοξιτίνη (100%), στην πολυμυξίνη Β (90%), στην αμοξικιλίνη-κλαβουλανικό οξύ (86%) και στην τετρακυκλίνη (73%). Χαμηλά επίπεδα αντοχής παρατηρήθηκαν έναντι της χλωραμφενικόλης C (18%) και της γενταμικίνης CN (10%). Το αποτέλεσμα μας έδειξε ότι στελέχη *E. coli*, συχνότατου αίτιου διάρροιας, απαιτούν τακτικό έλεγχο του επιπολασμού της αντοχής τους στα αντιμικροβιακά.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

αιματηρή διάρροια, EHEC, *Escherichia coli*, Βεροτοξίνη, αντιμικροβιακή αντοχή

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